

Siyakhula Collaborative Workshop

BACKGROUND

Globally each year, 1.3 million women living with HIV become pregnant¹

Access to antiretroviral therapies (ART) for pregnant and breastfeeding women is increasing, and the population of HIV-exposed, *uninfected* (HEU) infants is rising^{2,3}

It remains unclear how the persistent inflammation, immune dysfunction, and metabolic abnormalities experienced by pregnant and breastfeeding HIV+ women on ART⁴⁻⁶ shape development of the *uninfected* infant

WORKSHOP GOALS

- Bring together a group of international, multidisciplinary health scientists, clinicians, and other stakeholders
- Build capacity for research and training in HIV-infection and women's and infants' health across geographical and disciplinary boundaries

MULTI-STAKEHOLDER DISCUSSION HIGHLIGHTS

Understanding health risks for HEU infants

- **Neurodevelopment, immune and growth outcomes** associated with HEU remain poorly understood
- **Lack of breastfeeding** may impair infant immune development, increasing risk of secondary infections
- **Transmission of HIV from mothers to infants** remains a health risk
- **High diversity among HEU infants** (including increasing language diversity, cultural differences and health profiles) requires community-based, individualised approaches

ART: education, safety and compliance

Challenges

- **Extensive misinformation** and/or lack of communication exists around ART treatment, side effects and why compliance is important
- Low health literacy/poor understanding of conditions, and health outcomes possible with ART may be a barrier to compliance

Opportunities

- **Women must be empowered to engage in their care decisions** and communicate what they need to help them comply with their treatment regimens
- **Health workers** must engage with and **deliver on the spoken needs** of women

Safe breastfeeding practices

Challenges

- **Women receive mixed messages** about the safety and importance of exclusive breastfeeding (BF)
- **Recommended timelines for exclusive and duration of BF are unrealistic and often unattainable**
- **Food insecurity** is a clear barrier to prolonged BF and optimal maternal/child nutrition

Opportunities

- **Policies** to support BF need to be **community-centred**
- Dietitians and social workers play an important role in educating families to improve nutrition
- **Prioritisation of children** in the household for **nutrition access** is important

Opportunity

Partners, families and health workers need to be involved in each of these opportunities to support women

WHAT WE LEARNED

Misinformation between women and health workers is a barrier to ART compliance and exclusive breastfeeding, exacerbating the health risks faced by HEU infants

Support systems are key – health care workers, care providers, and communities need to be **educated on how to support women** in ART adherence and breastfeeding

The effects of **co-occurring exposure to HIV and ARTs in the womb, along with malnutrition** pre- and postnatally, on neurodevelopment, immune and growth outcomes in infants and children need to be better understood

References

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